

yield for rice, but caused it to decline drastically in wheat planted in fine-textured soil, indicating that P release in fine-textured soils is adversely affected by CaCO₃ under dryland cropping.

Differences in P release may be caused by temperature and soil moisture conditions. Submerging the soil released the P due to CO₂ pressure by converting CaCO₃ to CaHCO₃ and H₂CO₃, which makes insoluble P soluble. Higher temperatures

Table 2. Olsen's extractable P related to temperature and period of submergence, Ludhiana, India.

Soil	Multiple regression equation	R value ^a
Loam	$y = 0.1064 x_1 + 0.7615^{**} x_2 - 0.0023 x_1 x_2 - 25.545$	0.89**
Sandy loam	$y = 0.314^{**} x_1 + 1.075^{**} x_2 - 0.00884^{**} x_1 x_2 - 35.961$	0.88**

^a**Significant at 1% level. y = Olsen's extractable P (ppm), x₁ = period of submergence (d), x₂ = av max soil temp (°C).

also increased P solubility. The effects of temperature and submergence are illustra-

ted by the multiple regression equations for loam and sandy loam soils in Table 2. □

Determining ammonium content in wetland soil extracts using an ammonia electrode

G. Keerthisinghe, K. Mengel, and S. K. De Datta, IRRI

We studied whether an ion-specific electrode could be used to determine the ammonium concentration in soil extracts, because the method is faster than conventional ones. We tested 1.0 N KCl extracts (soil:solution = 1:10) of 54 soil samples from 3 main rice growing areas of the Philippines – Maligaya, Cabuyao, and Iloilo.

Soil samples were taken 20 d after transplanting (DT). Ammonium concentration was measured with an ammonia electrode (Orion model 95-10) connected to a digital pH/mV meter calibrated for ammonium analysis. For low ammonium concentrations, the electrode was filled with a relatively dilute internal filling solution containing 5 mM NH₄Cl and 0.5 M NaNO₃. Sodium nitrate was added to inhibit osmotic interference. Instead of adding 1 ml of 10 M NaOH to 100ml

Relationship between indol-phenol blue method and ammonia electrode method of determining ammonium content of wetland soil extracts, IRRI.

of samples as indicated in the instruction manual to convert ammonium to ammonia, we added 2 ml of 0.25 M NaOH, which was enough to raise the pH above 11, as needed for the conversion.

To test the method's accuracy, aliquots

of the same soil extracts were analyzed by the Indolphenol blue method, a highly sensitive colorimetric method for detecting ammonium. The positive correlation between results of the two methods was highly significant (see figure). □

Rice-Based Cropping Systems

Effect of rice straw mulching on wheat productivity

A. Motaleb Bhuiyan and Nur E-Elahi, Division of Rice Cropping Systems, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI), Joydebpur, Gazipur, Bangladesh

Farmers in Daudkandi, Bangladesh,

broadcast wheat following deep water rice. Wheat seeds often are eaten by birds, germination tends to be low, and during later plant growth, particularly flowering, moisture stress reduces grain yield. Using straw mulch can reduce these problems. In 1982-83, we studied the effect of rice straw mulching in a farm trial at the Rainfed Deepwater Rice-based Cropping

Systems Research site in Daudkandi. Broadcast or line-seeded wheat was mulched with deep water rice straw. Although the field was not weeded, mulch substantially reduced weeds. Unmulched plots had to be weeded twice. Mulched wheat yielded 2.9-3.0 t/ha and gave a higher net return, irrespective of planting method (see table). Mulching conserved

Effect of mulching on wheat yield under line and broadcast seeding, Daudkandi, Bangladesh, 1982-83.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)	Return ^a (\$/ha)	Total variable cost ^b (\$/ha)	Net return (\$/ha)
Line seeding, mulch	3.0	381	147	234
Line seeding, no mulch	2.5	317	145	172
Broadcast, mulch	2.9	368	144	224
Broadcast, no mulch	2.3	292	143	149

^a Wheat price = \$127/t. ^b Price of straw-mulch (\$17/ha) was also included in the economic analysis. Design: randomized complete block, 3 replications; variety Sonalika. Fertilizer rate = 80-26-33 kg N-P-K/ha. Seed rate = 120 kg/ha.

soil moisture, protected seeds from birds, and reduced weed growth. Planting method had little effect on yield. □

Individuals, organizations, and media are invited to quote or reprint articles or excerpts from articles in the IRRN.

Announcements

Azolla newsletter

IRRI will begin publishing in August 1985 a semi-annual *Azolla Newsletter* for workers interested in azolla, blue-green algae, and biological N fixation. The newsletter will help workers to share information, to keep abreast of developments in the field, and to maintain current information on azolla specimen collections throughout the world.

The newsletter will include 1) abstracts of azolla publications, 2) current issues in azolla research and use, 3) reports and recommendations of azolla meetings, 4) news of live and herbaria specimen collections, and 5) specimen accession announcements.

The *Azolla Newsletter* was recommended at the International Workshop on Azolla Use at Fuzhou, China, 31 Mar to 5 Apr 1985. For a free subscription to the newsletter, write: Dr. Iwao Watanabe, Soil Microbiology Department, IRRI, P.O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines.

Contributions to the *Azolla Newsletter* should be sent to any of the five regional editors. They are Liu Chung-chu (Asia), Vice President, Soil and Fertilizer Institute, Fujian Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Fuzhou, Fujian, China;

T. A. Lumpkin (North and South America), Department of Agronomy, Washington State University, Pullman, WA 99164-6420, USA

Elizabeth G. Cutter (Europe), Department of Botany, University of Manchester, Manchester M13 9PL, United Kingdom;

B. W. Norton (Australia), Department of Agriculture, University of Queensland, St. Lucia, Queensland, Australia 4067; or

H. F. Diara (Africa), West Africa Rice Development Association, B.P. 96, Saint Louis, Senegal.

Rice straw as cattle feed

The National Livestock Development Board, Mahaweli Authority of Sri Lanka Draft Animal Program, Animal Science Department of the University of Peradeniya, and the Sri Lanka-Netherlands Livestock Development Program are planning an international seminar for extension workers and research fellows working with rice straw as cattle feed. For further information regarding the seminar, tentatively scheduled for mid-1985, write the Coordinator, Straw Utilization Project, P. O. Box 138, Kandy, Sri Lanka. □

Watanabe receives Japanese soil science award

I. Watanabe, head of the IRRI Soil Microbiology Department, received the 30th award of the Japanese Soil Science Society on 7 Apr 1985 for his research on N fixation in tropical rice fields.

Watanabe graduated from the University of Tokyo in 1955 and received his D Agr in 1961. He has published more than 150 papers on N fixation and transformation and mineral nutrition. □

Conservation of crop germplasm — an international perspective

Conservation of crop germplasm — an international perspective, edited by W. L. Brown, T. T. Chang, M. M. Goodman, and Q. Jones, is a collection of six papers presented at a symposium on crop germplasm sponsored by the Crop Science Society of America. Subject matter ranges from a detailed description of the essential elements of successful plant exploration to the broadly defined goals and operations of national and international germplasm programs. The gene resource programs of two international agricultural research centers and germplasm conservation as practiced at the National Seed Storage Laboratory, Fort Collins, Colorado, also are described.

Price is US\$11 plus \$0.75 for all orders from outside the United States. Payment must accompany the order. For further information, write: CSSA Headquarters Office, Attn. Book Order Department, 677 S. Segoe Road, Madison, WI 53711, USA. □

New IRRI publications

New publications are available for purchase at the Communication and Publications Department, Division R, IRRI, P. O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines:

IRRI highlights 1984

Illustrated guide to integrated pest management in rice in tropical Asia, by W. H. Reissig, E. A. Heinrichs, J. A.